

Application of computational models in Next Generation Risk Assessment activities at Unilever

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Abstract

Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) is defined as an exposure-led, hypothesis-driven risk assessment approach that integrates new approach methodologies (NAMs) to assure safety without the use of animal testing. In recent years, various systems and methods have been developed rapidly to address different challenges in this area due to factors such as ethical issues, regulatory considerations, and the need to assure the safety of chemicals more efficiently and robustly. Among such methods, computational models are more and more widely applied.

In this talk, a general introduction will be given on what NGRA is and how it is applied in Unilever for making safety decisions to protect our consumers. Then, some computational models that have been applied in NGRA in Unilever will be reviewed, which include physiologically based kinetic (PBK) modelling and simulation, dose response modelling, transcriptomics data analysis, Bayesian methods, Expert Knowledge Elicitation, etc. A case study will then be introduced briefly to demonstrate the application of some of the models to evaluate how protective NAMs could be when they are applied to NGRA. At the end of the talk, the potential for wider application of computational models, the challenges regarding the acceptance of such models in a wider community, as well as some proposals to tackle such challenges will be discussed.

In summary, by providing a few examples of computational models and how some of them are applied to assess the safety of a group of case study chemicals, this talk aims to demonstrate and promote the application of computational models in supporting safety decision making in NGRA and to propose some ideas to address the challenges regarding the acceptance of such models' application in NGRA.